

The Relationship of Mythopoeitics With Other Literary Genres: Mythopoeitic Elements in Fantasy, Fantasy, Horror and Other Genres

Axmedova Shaxnoza Ravshanbek qizi

2nd year doctoral student at Namangan State University

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Annotation: This thesis aims to analyze mythopoeitics and its relationship with literary genres. Mythopoeitics is a theory that studies how mythological images, motifs and structures are used in literary texts. The thesis examines how mythopoeitic elements are expressed in literary genres such as fiction, fantasy, and horror, how mythological images and themes in these genres are interconnected and complement each other. The research methodology consists of studying the basic principles of mythopoeitics and how these principles are implemented through literary genres. The thesis reveals the role of mythopoeitics in literature and its contribution to modern genres.

Keywords: Mythopoeitics, Literary genres, Science fiction and fantasy, Mythological images and motifs, and mythological images.

Introduction

Mythopoeitics in literary studies includes the analysis of how mythological elements are used in literary texts. This area has its own special place and importance, especially in genres such as fiction, fantasy, and horror. Mythological images and images become the main motifs in many works in these genres. The genres of fantasy and fantasy, in particular, are enriched with mythological images by depicting events and beings outside the real world. Thus, mythopoeitics plays an important role in creating the development of events, the psychological state of characters, and the general atmosphere in these genres.

Research methodology

This thesis is based on the methodology of scientific analysis of the expression of mythopoeitics in literary genres and their influence on each other. The following methods are used in the research:

1. Textual analysis - the study of the forms of expression of mythopoeitic elements in literary works.
2. Intertextual analysis - the analysis of how mythological images are renewed in other genres and their changes in them.
3. Comparative analysis - comparing mythopoeitic elements in the genres of fiction, fantasy, and horror.[1]

Mythopoeitics and its relationship to literary genres is a specific area of literary studies that studies how mythological images, motifs, and structures are expressed in literary texts. Mythopoeitics reveals the relationship between mythology and literature, as mythological characters, events, images, and motifs have been renewed in literature for centuries and have changed in different genres. In modern literature, these elements are manifested in unique forms in fiction, fantasy, horror, and other genres.

1. The uniqueness of mythopoetics

Mythopoetics is based mainly on mythological images and motifs. Mythology is a set of ideas that reflect the ancient beliefs, moral principles, and worldview of a people. In literature, mythological motifs and images not only reflect past beliefs, but also take on new forms in a modern environment. Mythopoetic elements add a certain motif, image, or theme to literature, enriching the text, deepening the characters, and allowing the reader to discover new meanings.[2]

2. Mythopoetics and fiction

The fantasy genre is the most common area of mythopoetics. Fantasy is a genre that describes events outside the real world, and it contains imaginary and probable situations. Mythological images are widely used in the fantasy genre, as they form the basis of the fantastic world. For example, J.R.R. In Tolkien's works *The Hobbit* and *The Lord of the Rings*, mythological images (elves, orcs, dragons) and motifs (great battles, evil forces, heroism) play an important role. Tolkien's work not only creates a mythological world, but also contains traces of ancient myths.

In the fantasy genre, mythopoetic elements, for example, by creating images of a certain "hero" or "evil force", present a worldview, moral aspects, and critical thinking. The connection between fantasy and mythopoetics is that mythological motifs are used to create a fantasy world and its laws.[3]

3. Mythopoetics and fantasy

The fantasy genre also reflects mythopoetic elements, but in this genre, fantasy includes more imaginary and magical elements. The connection between fantasy and mythopoetics is that the fantasy world is often enriched with ancient myths, legends, magical creatures, and events. For example, in the *Harry Potter* series by J.K. Rowling, mythological elements are widely used: magic, magical creatures, the trials of heroes and ancient magical books - all this is closely related to mythology. In the fantasy genre, mythopoetics is its main mechanism, helping to create a fantastic and imaginary world.

4. Mythopoetics and horror

The horror genre makes extensive use of mythopoetic elements, as this genre works with mythological images and dark, mysterious images to create fear. In the horror genre, mythopoetics is often manifested through death, demons, spirits, dark forces and other mystical beings. The works of Stephen King, for example, "The Dog" or "The Shining" make extensive use of mythological elements. Their works show dark forces, dragons, demons or other terrible creatures, which frighten the main characters of literary works and have a psychological effect.

5. Mythopoetics and other genres

Mythopoetics is also used in other genres. For example, in detective or romantic literature, that is, other genres are also transformed with the help of mythopoetic elements. In detective works, mythological motifs can appear as mysterious or legendary events, while in romantic works, images of ancient loves, love spells, or fateful events in life are sometimes used.

Conclusion

Mythopoetics plays an important role not only in classical literature, but also in modern fiction, fantasy, and horror genres. These genres use elements related to mythology to update mythological images in their own unique way, expand time and space, and create new forms of life. While mythological motifs are usually combined with fantastic worlds and characters in the fantasy and fantasy genres, mythological characters and events are used in the horror genre to create fear and psychological tension. At the same time, mythopoetics serves as an important tool for creating innovation in literature and brings complementary, innovative elements to different genres. In this way, the connection of mythopoetics with literary genres not only increases its aesthetic value, but also demonstrates the influence of mythology on modern literature.

REFERENCES:

1. Абдуллаев А. Основы литературоведения. – Ташкент: Ўқитувчи, 2011. – 320 с.
2. Qodirov M. Mythology and literature. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2007. – 250 p.
3. Abdullayeva S. Mythological images and motifs: literary analysis. – Tashkent: Adabiyot, 2014. – 280 p.
4. Kholmatov D. Uzbek fiction. – Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2010. – 312 p.
5. Mirzaakhmedov S. The horror genre and its place in Uzbek literature. – Tashkent: Ta'lim, 2015. – 275 p.
6. King S. It. – New York: Viking Penguin, 1986. – 1138 p.
7. Cuddon J.A. A Dictionary of Literary Terms and Literary Theory. – London: Wiley-Blackwell, 2013. – 784 p.
8. Lévi-Strauss C. Structural Anthropology. – New York: Basic Books, 1963. – 352 p.
9. Campbell J. The Hero with a Thousand Faces. – Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1949. – 416 p.